
D3.4 Policy Brief 1

Can European small country productions be competitive?

Policy recommendations based on CresCine's "State of the art of WP3 European small film markets vs international competitors", CresCine's initial Skills Study and research on the festival circulation of European film.

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Document Change Log

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Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgment of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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Executive Summary

CRESCINE – Increasing the international competitiveness of the film industry in small European markets (HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01, project ID: 101094988) set to increase the competitiveness of the audiovisual and film sector of the small European markets, has recently conducted a comprehensive study into the various competitiveness markers of small territories, alongside a foray into the state of skills and festival visibility. The project has released an interactive report enabling stakeholders to perform deep dives into the state of seven European territories across different entry points of the value chain from development to exhibition, production to exports and more. The report "[Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons](#)," outlines key performance indicators and comparative analyses of seven small and six large markets from 2014 to 2022. The report discusses the different avenues large and small markets in the EU have found towards sustainable film industries. Among the large markets it evidences a clear strategic focus on export. The small markets studied differ in the ways they sustain their national film industries by either choosing one or combining several of the following models: cultural resonance, export, production service, and cinematic art.

This policy brief presents the key findings of the report to share insight into the different ways the national markets in the EU operate and to stimulate discussion on how national and supra-national policymakers can enhance the competitiveness of the audiovisual and film industry in small European territories. It also highlights the obstacles faced by small European film markets as well outlines seven strategies and discussion starters for policymakers, decision makers and industry executives. For example: **most popular titles domestically and internationally reveal minimal overlap between films that perform well at the domestic box office and those that achieve high non-domestic admissions.**

Furthermore, this policy brief sets the report's research findings into the context of challenges facing the European audiovisual industries at large, including the necessity to upskill its creative workforce. Therefore, this brief also draws on CresCine's initial Skills Study conducted in partnership with the European Film Academy in 2024 as a part of the inaugural Members survey and gathered the responses of more than 900 European film professionals.

Introduction: The challenges of small film markets in Europe

21 countries in the EU have fewer than 18 million inhabitants, which characterizes them as small audiovisual markets. This group of markets is not only characterized by a comparatively lower number of potential domestic audiences for their audiovisual productions, but also by a number of structural challenges that policy makers on both national and supra-national level need to be mindful of.

Small audiovisual industries' competitiveness is challenged by:

- limited funding for production, both through public and private means;
- low and/or fluctuating output of productions that make exhibitors and audiences dependent on imports;
- their unique cultural and linguistic profiles (sometimes even with different markets in the same country);
- small-scale production ecologies with a limited talent pool with few resources for training, a dominance of small and medium sized enterprises vulnerable to crisis as also highlighted by the Commission's MEDIA Industry Outlook 2023;
- distribution networks and exhibition opportunities dominated by foreign entities (often from the US).

Beyond these specific challenges for small audiovisual markets, the European and indeed international media industries are facing the tasks of:

- recovering from the loss of resources, audiences and creative restrictions during the Covid-19 pandemic;
- adapting to different transformations of the traditional producer-distribution-exhibitor value chains, through vertical integration and consolidation on the one hand, and the bypassing a range of intermediaries on the other;
- adapting to the growth in audiovisual streaming that challenges traditional exhibition windowing structures, but potentially also drives investment and distribution opportunities;
- navigating the impact of the macro-economic decline across many Western countries resulting in layoffs and bankruptcies, and declining revenues in an industry that is already characterized by high levels of personal and employment adapting to the technological transformations brought about by Generative Artificial Intelligence with their broader implications for employment, copyright and gatekeeping in the industry;
- issues at the heart of the 2023/24 writers' strike;
- responding to the evident necessity of greener and more sustainable production.

These specific challenges to small markets and the necessity to adapt to crisis and change are the context for the policy recommendations made in this brief. Based on the findings from the CresCine project made between spring 2023 and 2024, we make recommendations on two levels: 1) Increasing the understanding and mindfulness towards

the challenges of small markets, 2) Shaping future training initiatives that help the industry adapt to the changes it faces.

CresCine’s “Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons” research and interactive report

The project CRESCINE – Increasing the international competitiveness of the film industry in small European markets (HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01, project ID: 101094988) This project brings together over 20 leading academic and industry partners¹ across the European domain.

CresCine underscores the economic and cultural significance of local film industries in seven small countries and regions: Ireland, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania, Portugal, Croatia, and Flanders in Belgium. The selected markets and industries represent considerable diversity in terms of language characteristics, population, surface area, geography, political-historical background, and film cultural traditions.

The project’s research report, titled “[Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons](#),” has gathered empirical evidence for the traits and differences of the seven markets relative to each other, as well as in comparison with larger European markets. Their development is tracked from 2014 to 2022, considering factors such as production volume, genre patterns, funding sources, availability in VoD catalogues, distribution, admissions, and festival recognition. The report also compares the seven small markets with six large markets in Europe, analysing the role of partnerships in film export to different export territories, success of films on VOD, and festival success of films, and analyses the effects of US films on local industries.

This study, undertaken by Jakob Isak Nielsen, Cathrin Bengesser, Ivana Kostovska, Marius Øfsti, Ulrike Rohn and Ana Falcon, with contribution from other consortium partners focused on the comprehensive analysis of various performance markers and global competitive comparison, characterising the competitiveness potential of the seven European territories listed above. The research was based on data from Lumiere Pro, EAO Yearbook, Lumiere VoD, Eurostat, and national sources, such as the national film boards.

The study, published both as a consortium deliverable and an interactive report², is based on the analysis and visualisation of data from 2014-2022. Available at the CresCine website (<https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries/>), it also presents a unique four-avenue model of industry configuration, performance indicators deep dive across the value chain from production, funding, distribution, exhibition, and reception, and a wide comparison with six larger markets (Germany, France, the UK, Spain, Italy, and Poland) based on considering film export, films in VoD catalogues, and festival awards.

¹ <https://www.crescine.eu/consortium>

² <https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries>

Figure 1. CresCine’s “Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons” interactive website

The interactive report allows readers to understand the dynamics of the different stages of the film industries’ value chain and the specific ways small and large markets have found to stay competitive in a global market. Understanding these differences and idiosyncrasies is important for ensuring a balanced approach between the needs of different market types. In the following we summarise key insights on the strengths and weaknesses of small film markets.

1. None of the investigated European small country ecosystems possess a home market robust enough to sustain a film industry independently.
2. Four market models or “avenues” emerge as crucial ‘orientation options’ for small markets: cultural ‘resonance’, export, production service, and cinematic art. Different markets exhibit various configurations.
3. Striking a balance between investment-focused and output quality domestic productions proves challenging.
4. In the small markets there is little overlap between the films that perform well domestically and those that export successfully. Animation films, as well as family and children’s films, punch above their weight when it comes to exports in particular ‘and are promising targets for export. Comedy, on the other hand, stands out as a genre that performs better in domestic markets relative to its share in the output of films. This is also the genre where US-imports are least competitive. .

5. A key challenge for small markets is maintaining a diversity of genres in their production. There is a significant overemphasis on drama films, in some markets born out of hopes of festival and awards success, genre films (e.g., adventure, fantasy, sci-fi, horror, family) can drive more export-oriented success and circulation on VoD
6. Some but not all small markets can benefit from export factors that also drive the performance of larger markets, namely the English language, language sharing with other markets, co-production, known auteurs and talent, tapping into internationally well-known phenomena, exposure and success at international festivals.
7. The small markets in the EU differ greatly in their share of domestic admissions. Increasing domestic admissions requires a comprehensive strategy across the value chain, including public support from development to marketing, successfully stimulating private investment, having a viable distribution and exhibition infrastructure, and a creative ecosystem interested in and capable of producing films with wide appeal.
8. Global streamers offer a limited selection of films from small territories, hence domestic and European VOD buyers can present an opportunity for increasing local and regional circulation and providing revenue to filmmakers.
9. Films from small countries receive less visibility at major A-class and FIAPF certified festivals. Research, based on the analysis of data from the Marche Du Films “Cinando” database, not conducted within CresCine but presented in synergy with the projects findings at the CresCine conference at the Marche Du Film 2024 clearly demonstrates that **films from small countries were on the margins of international film festivals.**³
10. The attention to films from small countries improved marginally over time, and the films were primarily programmed outside the main industry events. Looking more closely at the films that receive festival recognition reveals that films that have broad appeal rarely appear in the most prestigious sections of the top three festivals or win the most coveted awards but do well in other festivals and the awards ceremonies.
11. Given that none of the seven eco-systems have a domestic market strong enough to sustain a local film industry, the report suggests that small European film eco-systems pursue four avenues in order to address this key challenge: cultural ‘resonance’, export, production service and cinematic art. Some small film ecosystems align more clearly with one avenue. On other occasions, they are pursuing more avenues at the same time though often with different degrees of intensity. The four avenues can be presented as seen below.

³ <https://www.vejune-zemaityte.com/publication/quantifying-the-global-film-festival-circuit/>

Orientation towards....	Cultural 'resonance'	Export	Production service	Cinematic art
Legitimacy	National-cultural relevance	International success	Job creation & GDP	Artistic recognition
Primary policy fields	Cultural policy	Trade policy	Employment policy Finance policy Tourism policy	Cultural policy
Success criteria	Cultural policy goals (e.g. high <u>domestic market shares</u>)	Foreign <u>sales</u> , <u>circulation</u> , <u>user metrics</u> , commercial profits	Employment & fiscal goals (e.g. <u>incoming investments</u> , local expenditure)	<u>Awards</u> , <u>nominations</u> , critical accolades (e.g. festival & critical recognition)

Table 1. Overview of “four avenues” of film ecosystem configurations presented in the Small Markets interactive report.

The table illustrates that the four avenues stand out from each other in a number of respects. They are couched within different policy contexts. They are based on different forms of legitimacy. They are also guided by different success criteria. The sources of funding also typically vary. The implication is also that each avenue stimulates the production of particular kinds of films – and in the case of production service often international productions rather than domestic productions.

CresCine’s Skills Study

In 2024 CresCine conducted in partnership an investigation into the state of the skills of established European film professionals. This was undertaken as a part of the first-ever Members survey of the European Film Academy with more than 900 respondents participating in the survey. The findings of the survey are available as designated overview at the CresCine website (<https://www.crescine.eu/blog/efa-crescine-members-survey-2023>) as well as were communicated widely to the industry at Crescine’s sessions at Industry@Tallinn & Baltic Event 2023 and Berlinale EFM 2024.

Figure 2. European film industry professionals rarely take part in training annually according to the study conducted by CresCine and European Film Academy.

According to the results, established **professionals in the European film industry are confronting high levels of personal and employment insecurity**. This translates into limited opportunities for annual training and upskilling, as demonstrated by the collaborative skills study conducted by CresCine in partnership with the European Film Academy. The study, cognisant of its structural and territorial limitations, is currently being expanded to cover a broad range of European professionals, sectors, and markets.

However, the results of the study, which have been widely disseminated among industry and policymaking stakeholders, paint a **bleak picture of the structural mismatch between the industry reality, the skills offered, and the personal financial and motivational capacity to upskill to meet the current requirements of the marketplace**.

Our findings reveal that only 20% of all respondents feel secure about their position in the industry when it comes to future prospects or their financial capacity to stay up-to-date and competitive. A significant 80% of all respondents do not feel secure within the industry and cannot attend training programmes, even if they wish to. Only 30% of all respondents indicate they have the financial support to participate in training programmes.

Simultaneously, more than 80% of all respondents believe that increasing diversity and inclusion within the European film industry is important. Nearly 50% of the participating Academy members value the European Film Academy's efforts towards promoting diversity and inclusion in its work. However, 25% believe the European Film Academy is doing an

excellent job in this respect, while the remaining 75% indicate they are unsure or believe that improvements can be made. Racism and sexism (57%), the need for non-stereotyped storytelling (40%), and easy accessibility to the industry through fair distribution in funding (25%) are seen as the most significant issues in European cinema.

Last but not least, more than 50% of all correspondents consider a transition to a sustainable European film industry important. When it comes to sustainability, the reduction of carbon emissions, fair labour practices/social equity, and the sustainable sourcing of materials and products are most often mentioned as the most crucial topics.

Our Policy Recommendations

The following section delineates our principal policy recommendations, which are predicated on our interactive markets report⁴, our skills study's preliminary findings⁵, and CresCine researchers' investigation into festival circulation⁶. As previously indicated, these policy recommendations are intended to initiate dialogue among decision-makers, policy executives, and industry leaders, aiming for a better alignment between industry aspirations, policy objectives, and the actual state of the markets. These policy recommendations can be supplemented by in-depth resources published on the CresCine website at <https://crescine.eu>.

1. One Size Does Not Fit All (European Territories)

For a small market with limited resources, the reality often involves “pitching in all directions” to secure resources for the development of its audiovisual and film industry. This includes striving for “cultural excellence” for the national cultural agenda, festival and awards success for public decision-makers and the national audience, exports and competitiveness for business development programs (often backed by EU structural funds), VOD and digital availability for innovation policy, among others.

Our empirical findings clearly demonstrate that **one size does not fit all Some ecosystems align more closely with one avenue. Many pursue a combination of avenues. Whereas all avenues are – theoretically – available to any small film ecosystems, it is extremely unlikely to achieve success and traction in all directions.** This implies that global artistic festival successes, backed by a worldwide streaming deal, a domestic box office hit with a global export-focused co-production, are highly improbable.

⁴ <https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries>

⁵ <https://www.crescine.eu/blog/efa-crescine-members-survey-2023>

⁶ <https://www.vejune-zemaityte.com/publication/quantifying-the-global-film-festival-circuit/>

Instead, a country or **ecosystem may choose a particular configuration of avenues** that can amplify its structural strengths while mitigating its weaknesses or become a future orientation for the industry.

2. Small Markets Must Make Difficult Choices

In the context of a global sectoral crisis, small markets face challenging decisions. Our comparative study indicates that **no single market consistently outperforms others when evaluated against the established success criteria.**

The industry's preoccupation with incoming productions not only inflates the costs for local productions but also limits the availability of creative professionals for local films. In theory, small markets can support the production of films targeting each of the four proposed types of legitimacy. However, two primary issues arise. Firstly, a low production volume results in a significant dependence on individual films. Secondly, each path aligns with a specific ecosystem logic, which includes a funding infrastructure, a distinct talent pool, a distribution and exhibition landscape, and a marketing setup customised for these productions. For instance, financing films that aim for cultural 'resonance' requires a range of additional conditions along the value chain. This includes storytellers who are both interested in and skilled at creating stories with cultural 'resonance', distributors who can effectively market these local films, and an audience willing to invest their time and money in them.

3. Play the hand you are dealt

While all four pathways are theoretically accessible to all industries, contextual factors influence the feasibility of pursuing certain paths. For instance, achieving successful circulation in Video-on-Demand catalogues is more challenging in markets with low domestic VoD penetration.

Our analysis of the **most popular titles domestically and internationally reveals minimal overlap between films that perform well at the domestic box office and those that achieve high non-domestic admissions.** This illustrates how an orientation towards cultural resonance may be difficult to reconcile with an export orientation in small markets with limited output. A shift in orientation may be challenging if an ecosystem is already oriented in a certain way. However, policy measures can assist markets in reconfiguring a market's orientation.

4. Assess Future Prospects

In the ongoing industry-wide crisis, experts across all domains tend to agree that increased funding and production do not equate to a healthier or more sustainable film industry.

Instead of asking “are we financing or producing enough”, countries and ecosystems should step back and consider broader perspectives such as “are we producing the right kinds of films and for whom”.

Our research indicates that culturally less celebrated films, such as genre films or animation films, tend to perform better internationally, whereas comedy films tend to yield box office results. Although not directly addressed in this report, successful films on streaming platforms tend to adhere to the platform’s editorial guidelines or direct commissions.

6. Prioritise and Actively Allocate Resources for Festival Strategies

As festival “success”, especially in A-class competitive programmes, is often linked to various positive outcomes including national pride, sales and distribution opportunities, and further festival exposure at the circuit, we recommend in the current environment that stakeholders **prioritise a 360-degree festival strategy with appropriate financial, strategic and staffing resourcing**. This involves liaising with key festival stakeholders in the early stages of production, updating and involvement in the editorial and rough-cut process, as well as active cultivation towards sales agents and agencies that enjoy strong relationships with major festivals, as “blind submissions to programming” are not guaranteed to deliver success.

7. Focus on skills

With the average lifespan of certain skills in the ever-digital and innovation-driven audiovisual sector marketplace (such as the impact of Virtual Production and generative Artificial Intelligence) becoming as short as 2.5 years⁷, we recommend policymakers and ecosystem executives to **consider shifting focus from content-centric thinking to skills-centric thinking**. This will ensure that their stakeholders are informed of training opportunities, are offered a diverse range of training options and opportunities including financial support, and diversify the training portfolio between festivals and markets, professional training programmes and e-learning/self-learning. Finally, concrete market and evaluation strategies should be put in place to ensure that the market demand meets the industry skill readiness and offering. We are looking forward to support this dialogue by an additional skills study conducted in May-June 2024 amongst European industry stakeholders with preliminary results released in July 2024.

⁷ <https://hbr.org/2023/09/reskilling-in-the-age-of-ai>

Conclusion. Start a conversation on “what constitutes success for small markets and for whom”.

We wish to conclude this policy brief with a call to action initiating a dialogue on “what constitutes success” for small European markets and for whom and on how the competitiveness of small markets can be improved in ways that are mindful of their idiosyncrasies that stem from their different market orientations i.e. how these markets can improve their value propositions.

As demonstrated above, for small European markets and the EU in general, a one-size-fits-all approach tends not to be effective. In fact, the differences in the way the markets position themselves evidence European diversity and promise diversified pathways to resilience and competitiveness. This necessitates a nuanced and multi-layered strategy to bring stakeholders together to identify what constitutes success and to balance national cultural agendas, festival success requirements, economic investments, export goals, and last but not least, a well-trained, market-ready industry actively engaging with its audience.

A country may choose to focus on one or try to combine features of several of the four avenues and become a regional or even European leader in a specific industry, achieving success relative to the political, structural, and fiscal resources provided. However, to accomplish this, stakeholders across national public and private sectors must align and agree on the focus areas and what constitutes success for the country, a market, or Europe as a whole.

We at CresCine are eager to facilitate this dialogue with further industry studies, reports, and insights available at crescine.eu, and through direct contact with the consortium, its individual member organisations, researchers, or representatives.